

Indicators of Successful Weaning from Renal Replacement Therapy in the Intensive Care Unit

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Abstract

This dissertation explores key indicators for the successful weaning of patients from Renal Replacement Therapy (RRT) in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Addressing the complications associated with RRT, the study emphasizes the importance of evidence-based strategies and timely initiation. Acute kidney injury affects a substantial number of individuals, leading to a significant need for RRT in critical cases. The research underscores the risks and potential adverse effects of prolonged RRT, emphasizing the need to identify the optimal time for discontinuation to prevent negative consequences. The methodology involves a systematic review and meta-analysis, examining existing literature to identify markers and predictors of successful RRT weaning. The results highlight urine output as a key variable, supported by multiple studies indicating its significance in predicting successful RRT discontinuation. The study also explores the roles of creatinine levels and diuretic therapy, offering a comprehensive overview of factors influencing the decision to wean patients from RRT. The study synthesizes findings, emphasizing the lack of consensus on certain indicators while underscoring the prominence of urine output. The conclusion highlights the importance of collaborative efforts among healthcare professionals, particularly critical care nursing, in monitoring patients and determining the optimal time for discontinuing RRT. Recommendations include the development of personalized guidelines, continuous education for healthcare teams, and regular monitoring of kidney function and fluid balance. In summary, this dissertation contributes insights into indicators for successful RRT weaning in the ICU, offering guidance for healthcare professionals to enhance patient outcomes and improve the quality of care in critical settings.

Keywords: acute kidney injury, continuous renal replacement therapy, intensive care, weaning, urine output, creatinine

Introduction

The UK Renal Registry (2018) reported that over 550,000 people develop acute kidney injury with approximately 60,000 requiring renal replacement therapy (RRT). This can be life-saving but does have complications associated with the procedure. To counter this measured intervention, approaches are employed to manage these issues (Wald et al., 2015). As new evidence-based research emerges surrounding RRT initiation strategies, such as beginning early versus late, there must also be a discussion on the optimal time to discontinue RRT in critically ill patients, and what markers are there to indicate this (Klouche, Gibney, and Forni, 2018).

After conservative management of fluid resuscitation, RRT is the next line of supportive management for patients who develop life-threatening fluid, acid-base, or electrolyte disorders (KDIGO, 2012). As with all medical interventions there are dangers associated with the treatment, namely the risks of catheter insertion for an extended duration, haemodynamic instability, hypothermia, electrolyte abnormalities, nutrient loss, and haemolytic complications from anticoagulation administration (Sigwalt et al., 2018).

With these prospects in mind, the critical care community must thoroughly assess whether RRT initiation would lead to the best outcomes, especially in patients without urgent indications as once the patient starts undergoing RRT there is a well-defined lead time to ceasing the treatment (Tandukar and Palevsky, 2018). The UK Renal Registry (2016) tallied a total of 592,212 deaths in 2016 from RRT patients. Likewise, in a prospective multicentre cohort study by Bagshaw et al. (2013), it concluded that hospital mortality was significantly higher, almost doubling, for RRT patients in comparison with non-RRT patients (62.4% vs 37.4%).

Given that prolonged RRT can promote poorer patient outcomes, increase hospital costs, and increase the likelihood of encountering adverse treatment effects (Kelly, Waikar, and Mendu 2019), it has also been found that extending the RRT period can potentially postpone kidney recovery increase dependency on medication over time (McCausland et al., 2016). As a consequence, there is an onus to identify when the patient can safely stop the treatment. Regardless, early discontinuation of RRT is not the best option for all circumstances (Frohlich et al., 2012), and early weaning in critically ill patients may contribute to higher mortality if the renal function has not fully recovered leading to systemic effects of ongoing AKI (Gemmell, Docking and Black, 2017).

Methods

The dissertation critically analysed the relevant literature to improve awareness and assess indications on the ideal time of when to safely wean from RRT in practice.

A systematic review and meta-analysis have been utilised to evaluate the ideal markers or predictors of successful weaning of RRT. Databases were searched and studies were screened using predefined keywords and criteria, however, the current pieces of evidence were inhibited by limitations. Studied parameters were included and, where possible, data was analysed to identify variables associated with successful discontinuation and the effect to patient outcomes.

Results

Discontinuing a course of RRT pertains to several different considerations such as biochemical criteria (creatinine, eGFR, and urea), kidney biomarkers (cystatin C), and physiologic characteristics (urine output, diuretic use, haemodynamic stability, and fluid balance) (Schiffl, 2018; Jones and Devonald, 2013). A systematic review and meta-analysis by Katulka *et al.* (2020) involving 23 studies revealed that urine output was the most common variable which suggests the indicator might be a good marker for successful RRT. Lee *et al.* (2017) concluded in a retrospective study including 165 patients that the urine output of the successfully weaned group was significantly higher than the non-successful group (55.7-66.3ml/hr vs 26.6-46.4ml/hr). On a similar note, the Artificial Kidney Initiation in Kidney Injury (AKIKI) trial by Gaudry *et al.* (2016) with 620 patients posited that the withdrawal of RRT once the urine output was 500 ml or higher per 24 hours should be considered, moving to a strong suggestion if the urine output was higher than 1000 ml per 24 hours without diuretics or higher than 2000 ml per 24 hours in patients receiving diuretics.

Further sources of evidence agree that urine output is a determining factor in identifying the optimal time to wean from RRT. Zarbock *et al.* (2016) recognised as urine output greater than 400 ml per 24 hours without diuresis and 2100 ml per 24 hours with diuretic therapy as key renal recovery parameters. Similarly, Viallet *et al.* (2016) concluded that a successful predictor of when to discontinue RRT was a urine output >2300 ml per 24 hours with diuretics. In addition, Katayama *et al.* (2016) established that RRT weaning was strongly associated with the urine output with prediction accuracy of AUROC (area under the curve) 0.814 which is considered excellent.

Another possible gauge for successful RRT weaning is a patient's creatinine level (Dewitte *et al.*, 2015). Gaudry *et al.* (2016) speculated that weaning RRT was necessary if there was an unprompted decline in serum creatinine with enough diuresis. Conversely, a further study by Katayama *et al.* (2016) recognised that although serum creatinine level was noteworthy and acceptable with an AUROC of 0.727, the discrepancy between the success and failure groups in RRT discontinuation was inconsequential. A different approach conducted by Viallet *et al.* (2016) utilised urinary creatine clearance (UCr) as a predictor for discontinuing RRT. The conclusions drawn were that a UCr of ≥ 5.2 mmol in 24 hours was linked with effective weaning in

84% of patients involved in the study. This phenomenon was further investigated in a cohort study by Aniert *et al.* (2016), which observed no difference between serum creatinine concentration and urinary creatinine concentration as a measure of effectiveness. Similarly, Lee *et al.* (2017) found no correlation between serum creatinine as a predictor of weaning RRT because of various factors (age, muscle mass, gender) that may affect the level.

An alternative school of thought on early discontinuation of RRT is the use of diuretic therapy to stimulate urination (Rosner *et al.*, 2014; Nadeau-Fredette and Bouchard, 2013). Jeon *et al.* (2018) revealed that the aggressive use of diuretic therapy was associated with successful RRT weaning. Patients who were treated with diuretics had higher urine output and better serum creatinine versus the non-diuretic cluster (619 vs 557 patients). Another study by Heise *et al.* (2012) concluded that diuretics administration contributed to the enhancement of kidney function while attempting to stop RRT. On the contrary, the use of diuretics to improve renal recovery or to increase RRT-free time was not recommended by KDIGO (2012) as the studies gathered didn't show any valuable improvement of administering diuretics in stopping RRT. To support the KDIGO findings, a study by Wu *et al.* (2012) which involved 572 patients, determined that there was no difference between the renal recovery between the diuretic versus non-diuretic groups. In addition to these findings, the 3-day accumulated dosage of using diuretics while in RRT could increase the mortality risk.

Discussion

In summary, after analysing various sources surrounding the indicators to successfully wean patients from RRT, there are three metrics regarding the health of a patient's renal system that has seen traction in recent times. Decreases in creatinine levels in both urinary and serum were equated to one another, but a consensus has yet to be reached linking this outcome to the optimal weaning effectiveness (Aniert *et al.*, 2016; Lee *et al.*, 2017). Diuretic therapy has been used to stimulate the renal system to demonstrate functionality, but official studies have not observed tangible benefits to the approach and advise against it (KDIGO, 2012; Wu *et al.*, 2012). Urine output was the only indicator to relish support from all sources analysed (Katulka *et al.*, 2020; Katayama *et al.*, 2016; Gaudry *et al.*, 2016; Viallet *et al.*, 2016; Zarbock *et al.*, 2016), with a tiered approach suggested in response to different prior treatments seemingly being adequate evidence for over three quarters of patients to be weaned in the surveyed studies, leading to better overall outcomes.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Currently, the verdict to stop RRT is strongly influenced by several clinical factors (Vanmassenhove *et al.*, 2018). Critical care nursing plays a huge impact on detecting the parameters on when is it safe to discontinue RRT as they are responsible for the 24-hour provision of keeping the patient safe and ensure good quality of care delivery (Richardson and Whatmore, 2015). Collaborative efforts by the multi-disciplinary team are essential to create a protocol on the parameters to consider when it is possible to stop RRT (Bonnassieux *et al.*, 2018). With all the recommendations from the studies, it is best to develop a suitable and personalised guideline or pathway fit and agreed by the whole team (Page *et al.*, 2014). Hourly fluid balance monitoring, taking into consideration the urine output, is a basic nursing intervention, nevertheless acknowledged as a key component in deciding when to wean patients from RRT (Asfour, 2016). In addition, regular monitoring of kidney function through diagnostic tests and checking of acid-base balance are crucial markers of renal function recovery in RRT patients (Wang *et al.*, 2021). As the advances in critical care have transformed into higher odds of survival- not only focusing on merely surviving but to a wider emphasis on quality of life, continuous education and specialised training for the health care teams are essential on striking the optimal time of weaning RRT promoting in-depth progression and evaluation of policies to improve RRT delivery in intensive care unit (Busch *et al.*, 2017; Graham and Lischer, 2011).

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